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ANALYSIS OF SOFTWARE COST ESTIMATION BASED ON THREE LAYERS OF METRICS

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Abstract:

Software development effort estimation is the process of forecasting the software effort to estimate software costs of both development and maintenance. Such estimates may be to analyze project investment. Software researchers and practitioners have provided effort estimation for several decades. Most of them focused on the construction of formal software effort estimation models, such as Putnam's SLIM, COOMO 81, COOMO II, COCOTS, Kemerer and Albrecht-Gaffney, that can be applied to measure on different project scales (small, medium, and large). We employed five software projects ranging from small (less than 10,000 SLOC) to medium (10,000 – 100,000 SLOC) scale for estimating software effort by means of the aforementioned estimation models. Conventional and object-oriented metrics were used to determine the relationship among metrics, efforts, and project size. All the above Models are based on Two layer Architecture of Software Cost Estimation.

“The single most important task of a project: setting realistic expectations.”

The New Enhanced Three layer Architecture of Software Cost Estimation is to tune the parameters of the COstructive Cost MOdel (COCOMO) and Function point method which is mostly used in corpoarte for estimation of Cost and Schedule.

Key Word: Product Attributes”, “Hardware Attributes”, “Personnel Attributes”, “Project Attributes

Process Model of the Estimation

The assertion of this work is that estimation of the amount of effort required for the development of a project. Software cost estimation process is a set of techniques and

procedures that is used to derive the software cost estimate but it has many failure and causes the Software Crisis

Software Project Estimation

The four basic steps in software project estimation are:

- 1) Estimate the size of the development product. This generally ends up in either Lines of Code (LOC) or Function Points (FP), but there are other possible units of measure. A discussion of the pros & cons of each is discussed in some of- the material referenced at the end of this report.
- 2) Estimate the schedule in calendar months.

The ability of a company to compete effectively in the increasingly competitive global market is influenced to a large extent by cost [1]. Cost is the expenditure necessary for the attainment of a goal;

Costing and pricing:

1. Estimates are made to discover the cost, to the developer, of producing a software system.
2. There is not a simple relationship between the development cost and the price charged to the customer.

Advantages: You get the contract

Disadvantages: The probability that the customer gets the system he or she wants is small. Costs do not accurately reflect the work required.

- How do you know what customer has?

1.4.1. Cost Models

Early cost model were linear but it has been shown there is no clear linear relationship between effort and size.

Later cost models were generally based on the following non-linear formula:

$$E = (a + b*(SIZEc)) * f(x_1 \dots , x_n)$$

Base formula correction, (depends on the value of entities (x1, . . . xn)

where E = effort

a, b and c are derived constants and

x₁ to x_n are influencing factors which vary from project to project.

Boehm's CoCoMo

There are three forms of the CONstructive COst MOdel :

Basic CoCoMo which gives an initial rough estimate of man months and development time,

Intermediate CoCoMo which gives a more detailed estimate for small to medium sized projects,

Detailed CoCoMo which gives a more detailed estimate for large projects.

Basic CoCoMo

Calculates a cost estimate based on project size using the following equations:

Table 1.4.2.1.1 – Basic COCOMO Data

Organic mode	Semi-detached mode	Embedded mode
$MM_d = 2.4(KDSI)^{1.05}$	$MM_d = 3.0(KDSI)^{1.12}$	$MM_d = 3.6(KDSI)^{1.20}$
$MM_{am} = 1.0 (ACT) (MM_d)$	$MM_{am} = 1.0 (ACT) (MM_d)$	$MM_{am} = 1.0 (ACT) (MM_d)$

Where, MM_d: the time, in man-months, to develop the software.

MM_{am}:the time, in man-months, to maintain the software

TDEV:development schedule in months

KDSI:number of thousands of delivered source instructions

ACT:annual change traffic, i.e. the average fraction of a product's source instructions that are changed in one year.

Point of Estimation And Discription

Derived Method is not suitable for atypical projects. They are Calibrated to past not future. They disregard components not included in the model.

In Delphi or Shang Technique, an expert knows what the right value is but is unable to explain why it is so. Thus here also certain problem occurs.

- This method cannot be quantified.
- It is hard to document the factors used by the experts or experts-group.

Proposed Solution

The Three-point estimation technique, is used to improve direct estimation, when more values are provided by estimators. It is one of the general estimating methods that helps project managers produce better estimates.

Three Point Estimation

This method is used when more values are provided by estimators. This is a technique to improve direct estimation. It is one of the general estimating methods that helps project managers produce better estimates.

Three Point Estimation Technique

A direct estimation is improved by the use of three-point estimation technique , this is a technique to improve direct estimation , when more values are provided by estimators.

- **Most likely (approx. realistic scenario):** The duration of the schedule activity, given the resources likely to be assigned, their productivity, realistic expectations of availability for the schedule activity, dependencies on other participants, and interruptions.
- **Pessimistic (worst-case scenario):** The activity duration is based on a worst-case

scenario of what is described in the most likely estimate, where everything goes wrong.

Given the Minimum, the Most Likely, and the Maximum Value for the size, the activity duration estimate can be constructed, which is:

$$E = (\text{Min} + 4 \times \text{MostLikely} + \text{Max}) / 6$$

with standard deviation:

$$\sigma = (\text{Max} - \text{Min}) / 6 \quad \text{Where,}$$

E is a weighted average and SD measures the variability or uncertainty in the estimate.

The Three-Tier-Technique can be understood by through PERT (Program, Evaluation, and Review Technique) for Duration values.

Critical Path Method: The longest possible continuous pathway taken from the initial event to the terminal event. It determines the total calendar time required for the project; and, therefore, any time delays along the critical path will delay the reaching of the terminal event by at least the same amount.

The essential technique for using CPM is to construct a model of the project that includes the following:

A list of all activities required to complete the project (typically categorized within a work breakdown structure),

- The time (duration) that each activity will take to complete,
- The dependencies between the activities and,

Figure 2.4.2.1 – Critical Path Schedule.

Critical Activity: An activity that has total float equal to zero. An activity with zero float is not necessarily on the critical path since its path may not be the longest.

Lead Time: the time by which a predecessor event must be completed in order to allow sufficient time for the activities that must elapse before a specific PERT event reaches completion.

lag time: the earliest time by which a successor event can follow a specific PERT event.

Cost estimation techniques

Algorithmic cost modelling: A model is developed using historical cost information that relates some software metric (usually its size) to the project cost. An estimate is made of that metric and the model predicts the effort required [16].

Expert judgement: Several experts on the proposed software development techniques and the application domain are consulted.

Estimation by analogy: This technique is applicable when other projects in the same application domain have been completed.

Parkinson's Law: Parkinson's Law states that work expands to fill the time available. The cost is determined by available resources rather than by objective assessment.

Pricing to win: The software cost is estimated to be whatever the customer has available to spend on the project. The estimated effort depends on the customer's budget and not on the software functionality.

The COCOMO model:

A number of algorithmic models have been proposed as the basis for estimating the effort, schedule and costs of a software project. These are conceptually similar but use different parameter values. The model that I discuss here is the COCOMO model. The COCOMO model is an empirical model that was derived by collecting data from a large number of software projects. The first level (basic) provided an initial rough estimate; the second level

modified this using a number of project and process multipliers; and the most detailed level produced estimates for different phases of the project.

The sub-models [16] that are part of the COCOMO II model are:

1. An application-composition model: This assumes that systems are created from reusable components, scripting or database programming. It is designed to make estimates of prototype development.

2. An early design model: This model is used during early stages of the system design after the requirements have been established. Estimates are based on function points, which are then converted to number of lines of source code.

3. A reuse model: This model is used to compute the effort required to integrate reusable components and/or program code that is automatically generated by design or program translation tools. It is usually used in conjunction with the post-architecture model.

4. A post-architecture model: Once the system architecture has been designed, a more accurate estimate of the software size can be made

Software sizing

Software size is a key input to any estimating model and across most software parametric models. Supported sizing metrics include source lines of code (SLOC), function points, function-based sizing (FBS) and a range of other measures. They are translated for internal use into effective size (S_e). S_e is a form of common currency within the model and enables new, reused, and even commercial off-the-shelf code to be mixed for an integrated analysis of the software development process. The generic calculation for S_e is:

$$S_e = NewSize + ExistingSize \times (0.4 \times Redesign + 0.25 \times Reimpl + 0.35 \times Retest) \quad (6)$$

As indicated, S_e increases in direct proportion to the amount of new software being developed. S_e increases by a lesser amount as preexisting code is reused in a project. The extent of this

increase is governed by the amount of rework (redesign, re-implementation, and retest) required to reuse the code.

Function based sizing: While SLOC is an accepted way of measuring the absolute size of code from the developer's perspective, metrics such as function points capture software size functionally from the user's perspective. The function-based sizing (FBS) metric extends function points so that hidden parts of software such as complex algorithms can be sized more readily. FBS is translated directly into unadjusted function points (UFP). In SEER-SEM, all size metrics are translated to S_e , including those entered using FBS.

$$S_e = L_x \times (AdjFactor \times UFP)^{Entropy / 1.2}$$

Where,

- L_x is a language-dependent expansion factor.
- $AdjFactor$ is the outcome of calculations involving other factors mentioned above. Entropy ranges from 1.04 to 1.2 depending on the type of software being developed.

Effort and duration calculation

A project's effort and duration are interrelated, as is reflected in their calculation within the model. Effort drives duration, notwithstanding productivity-related feedback between duration constraints and effort. The basic effort equation is:

$$K = D^{0.4} \times \left(\frac{S_e}{C_{te}}\right)^E \tag{8}$$

Where,

- S_e is effective size - introduced earlier
- C_{te} is effective technology - a composite metric that captures factors relating to the efficiency or productivity with which development can be carried out. An extensive set of people, process, and product parameters feed into the effective technology rating. A higher rating means that development will be more productive
- D is staffing complexity - a rating of the project's inherent difficulty in terms of the rate at which staff are added to a project.
- E is the entropy - In days gone by entropy was fixed at 1.2. Next it evolved to 1.04 to 1.2 depending on project attributes with smaller IT oriented projects tending toward the lower.

Currently entropy is observed as 1.0 to 1.2 depending on project attributes. SEER will allow an entropy less than 1.0 if such a circumstance is observed as well.

Once effort is obtained, duration is solved using the following equation:

$$t_d = D^{-0.2} \times \left(\frac{S_e}{C_{te}}\right)^{0.4} \text{ ----- (9)}$$

The duration equation is derived from key formulaic relationships. Its 0.4 exponent indicates that as a project's size increases, duration also increases, though less than proportionally

“Full Function Points (FFP)” method was developed in 1997 [14]. It was a research project by the University of Quebec in cooperation with the Software Engineering Laboratory in Applied Metrics (SELAM). FFP method aimed to cover the area of real-time and embedded systems in addition to data strong systems by adding new data and transaction function types for measuring the real-time components. COSMIC FFP method, which is the second version of FFP, was published by Common Software Measurement International Consortium (COSMIC) in November 1999 [27]. This group has been established to develop this new method as a standardized one which would measure the functional size of software for business information systems, real-timesystems and hybrids of both. COSMIC FFP v.2.2 has been approved as being conformant to ISO/IEC 14143 and become an international ISO standard in 2003 [29]. Finnish Software Measurement Association (FiSMA) FSM method is developed by a working group of FiSMA [38]. It is designed to be applicable to all types of software. Similar to other methods based on “functionality”, FiSMA FSM is also based on functional user needs. The difference is that, FiSMA FSM is service-oriented instead of process-oriented. The importance of being able to estimate size of software earlier in the development life cycle has long been realized. In this context, Early Function Point Analysis (EFPA) technique was developed and subsequently refined [29], [40]. In 2000, Early & Quick COSMIC-FFP [41] was designed by the same research group to estimate the functional size of a wide range of software. In 2004, release 2.0 of these two early methods; are published [32]. Various approaches have been developed to adapt FPA to the needs of object-oriented (OO) software development. A widely referenced method is Object Points (OP) Method developed at the Leonard N. Stern School of Business, New York University [33]. The concepts underlying this method are very similar to that of FPA, except that objects, instead of functions, are being counted [24]. Other methods can be listed as Object Oriented Function Points Method [35], Predictive Object Points (POPs)

method [36] and OO-Method Function Points (OOmFP) [37]. In 1996, the International Standards Organization started a working group (ISO/IEC JTC1 SC7 WG12) on FSM to establish common principles of the methods based on “functionality”. They first published the first part of this standard [25], which defines the fundamental concepts of FSM such as “Functional Size”, “Base Functional Components (BFC)”, “BFC Types”, the FSM method characteristics and requirements that should be met by a candidate method to be conformant to this standard. The standard promoted the consistent interpretation of FSM principles. After that, IEEE Std. 14143.1, which is an adoption of ISO/IEC 14143-1:1998, was published [28]. Four more parts of ISO/IEC 14143, which are ISO/IEC 14143-2 [26]; ISO/IEC TR 14143-3 [27]; ISO/IEC TR 14143-4 [28]; ISO/IEC TR 14143-5 [39], were published in the following years (see Table 1). Currently, four methods have been certified by ISO to become an international standard; Mk II FPA v.1.3.1 [2], IFPUG FPA v.4.1 [18], COSMIC FFP v.2.2 [29], and NESMA FP v.2.2 [30].

Feature points

Caper Jones published method based closely on that of Albrecht called feature points with the aim of extending FSM to scientific algorithm. This method has been largely abandoned due to the intrinsic difficulty of sizing mathematical algorithms. It is an adaptation of FPA introduced by software productivity research in order to measure software size as well as business information systems.

. Fuzzy logic

The concept of fuzzy logic was given by Lotfi A. Zadeh in the year of 1965. In order to calculate vague and imprecise queries fuzzy logic is used. It is a multi-valued logic that uses different values between interval [0, 1]. According to Zadeh fuzzy set is defined as: “In universe of discourse U_x , a fuzzy subset A of U_x is characterised by a membership function $f_A(x)$ where $f(A):U_x [0, 1]$ ”. Fuzzy membership function associates with each member of X of U_x of a number of $f(x)$ in the interval [0, 1], represents degree of membership function of X in A . Linguistic variables are words whose values are imprecise e.g., very low, low, average, high, very high etc. To represent linguistic variables we use fuzzy numbers. Notions like rather tall or very fast can be formulated mathematically and processed by computers, in order to apply a more human-like way of thinking in the programming of computers [32]. Fuzzy systems is an alternative to traditional notions of set membership and logic that has its origins in ancient Greek philosophy [32]. The precision of mathematics owes its success in large part to the efforts of Aristotle and the philosophers who preceded him. In their efforts to devise a concise theory of logic, and later mathematics, the so-called ”Laws of Thought” were posited [32]. One of these, the ”Law of the Excluded Middle,” states that every

6.3. Triangular membership function (TFN)

Let $A_1 = (c_1, a_1, b_1)$ and $A_2 = (c_2, a_2, b_2)$ be two triangular fuzzy numbers as Fig. 1. The addition of A_1 and A_2 at h-level is:

$$A_{1(h)} \oplus A_{2(h)} = (L_{A_1(h)}^{-1} + L_{A_2(h)}^{-1}, L_{A_1(h)}^{-1} + R_{A_2(h)}^{-1}, R_{A_1(h)}^{-1} + L_{A_2(h)}^{-1}, R_{A_1(h)}^{-1} + R_{A_2(h)}^{-1})$$

L_{A_1} and R_{A_1} are the functions L and R of fuzzy number A_1 , respectively. $L_{A_1(h)}^{-1}$ and $R_{A_1(h)}^{-1}$ are the inverse functions of functions L_{A_1} and R_{A_1} at h-level, respectively. L_{A_2} and R_{A_2} are the functions L and R of fuzzy number A_2 , respectively. $L_{A_2(h)}^{-1}$ and $R_{A_2(h)}^{-1}$ are the inverse functions of functions L_{A_2} and R_{A_2} at h-level, respectively [32].

Suppose the membership functions of $A_1 = (c_1, a_1, b_1)$ is

$$f_{A_1}(x) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{(x-c_1)}{(a_1-c_1)}, c_1 \leq x \leq a_1, \\ \frac{(x-b_1)}{(a_1-b_1)}, a_1 \leq x \leq b_1, \\ 0, \quad \text{otherwise.} \end{array} \right\} \text{-----(14)}$$

Since

$$L_{A_1}(x) = \frac{(x - c_1)}{(a_1 - c_1)}, c_1 \leq x \leq a_1,$$

$$R_{A_1}(x) = \frac{(x - b_1)}{(a_1 - b_1)}, a_1 \leq x \leq b_1,$$

and

$$L_{A_1}^{-1}(h) = c_1 + (a_1 - c_1)h, \quad 0 \leq h \leq 1,$$

$$R_{A_1}^{-1}(h) = b_1 + (a_1 - b_1)h, \quad 0 \leq h \leq 1,$$

Similarly, suppose the membership function of $A_2 = (c_2, a_2, b_2)$ is

$$f_{A_2}(x) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{(x - c_2)}{(a_2 - c_2)}, \quad c_2 \leq x \leq a_2, \\ \frac{(x - b_2)}{(a_2 - b_2)}, \quad a_2 \leq x \leq b_2, \\ 0, \quad \text{otherwise.} \end{array} \right\}$$

Since

$$L_{A_2}(x) = \frac{(x - c_2)}{(a_2 - c_2)}, \quad c_2 \leq x \leq a_2,$$

$$R_{A_2}(x) = \frac{(x - b_2)}{(a_2 - b_2)}, \quad a_2 \leq x \leq b_2,$$

In our project there is fuzzy assessment of values assigned to the function points by the decision makers. There are many stakeholders involved in the process of software project development who acts as decision makers [6]. We rate linguistic variables i.e., very low, low, average, high and very high on the scale of 0 to 1 and derive weight using the formula of graded mean

integration given in equation 1. Suppose there are three stakeholders are involved who act as decision makers i.e., programmer (DM1), developer (DM2) and user (DM3). Each of them rate value of function point as very low, low, average, high or very high

Here, average of each fuzzy linguistic variable is calculated and formula of graded mean integration is applied on these values as shown below.

$$AV_{VL} = 0.246$$

$$AV_L = 0.337$$

$$A_A = 0.416$$

$$W = \frac{1}{6}(c + 4a + b)$$

$$W = 0.335$$

Where,

AV_{VL} is average value of linguistic variable Very Low

AV_L is average value of linguistic variable Low

A_A is average value of linguistic variable Average

W is weight of given linguistic variables

On applying the above formulas to remaining values, we obtained the following results:

Table 6.4.2 : Table showing calculated weights for each FPA attributes

FPA Attributes	DM1	DM2	DM3	Weights
External Input	VL	L	A	0.335
External Output	L	A	L	0.398
External Query	A	H	A	0.566
Internal Logical Files	H	VH	H	0.740
External Interface Files	H	A	A	0.849

Calculation of Fuzzy General System Characteristics

The fourteen general system characteristics are also rated as very low, low, average, high and very high by the decision makers. To calculate fuzzy weight of each GSC we use triangular

membership function and graded mean integration as discussed earlier. Three decision makers DM1, DM2, DM3 rate Data communication as VL, L and VL, to calculate the weight we use TFN as follows:

GSC1- Data Communication:

VL	0.00	0.191	0.255
L	0.255	0.321	0.495
VL	0.00	0.191	0.255

Here average of each value is calculated, and using average values weight is calculated.

$$A_{VL} = 0.085$$

$$A_L = 0.234$$

$$A_{VL} = 0.335$$

$$W = \frac{1}{6}(c + 4a + b)$$

$$W = 0.226$$

Where,

A_{VL} average of linguistic variable Very Low

A_L average of linguistic variable Low

W is weight

GSC2- Distributed Data Processing:

L	0.255	0.321	0.495
A	0.495	0.501	0.599
L	0.255	0.321	0.495

Here average of each value is calculated, and using average values weight is calculated as follows:

$$A_L = 0.335$$

$$A_A = 0.381$$

$$A_L = 0.529$$

$$W = \frac{1}{6}(c + 4a + b)$$

$$W = 0.398$$

Where,

AL average of linguistic variable Low

AA average of linguistic variable Average

AL average of linguistic variable Low

W is weight.

Table 6.5.1 - Fourteen General System Characteristics with their weights.

S.NO	14 GSC	DM1	DM2	DM3	Weights
1	Data Communication	VL	L	VL	0.226
2	Distributed Data Processing	L	A	L	0.390
3	Performance	H	VH	H	0.740
4	Heavily Used Configured	L	A	A	0.457
5	Transition Rate	H	H	A	0.616
6	Online Data Entry	L	VL	L	0.282
7	End User Efficiency	H	A	H	0.724
8	Online Update	L	L	VL	0.282
9	Complex processing	A	A	L	0.457
10	Reusability	VH	VH	H	0.813
11	Installation Ease	A	A	H	0.566
12	Multiple Site	A	H	A	0.566
13	Facilitate Change	VH	H	H	0.740
14	Operational Ease	L	VL	VL	0.225

$$\text{Complexity Adjustment Factor (CAF)} = 0.65 + 0.01 \times \sum (14 \text{ GSC}) \text{ -----(2)}$$

CONCLUSION

The Two layer Architecture of Software Cost estimation are not feasible to calculate the Cost and effort of any Software Project, so My research is completely focused on the Three Layers Based Software Cost Estimation.

COCOMO and Function Point models are based on Two layer Architecture of Software Cost estimation and that is not feasible to calculate the cost or schedule the Project development based on Software Development Life cycle is not feasible and the data collected from the 15 Top MNCs during my research are having a big margin of Actual Cost and the cost calculated from the COCOMO and Function Point models.

I have tried to develop a model for Three Layers Based Software Cost Estimation based on Influence Factor Redesign Optimization (IFRO) to tune the parameters of the COstructive COstModel (COCOMO). It is integrated with Influence Factor Function (IFF) methodology to assist decision making in software designing and development processes for achieving the exact cost of the project.

This Model will help the project managers to efficiently plan the overall software development life cycle of the software with accurate cost and schedule estimation.

Data on 15 large completed business projects data were collected and used to test the accuracy of the models and post effort estimation.

The input are feed in the program and set the variable and influence factors based on the Project Complexity and calculated the result and it approaches the accuracy till 93% from the actual cost of the developed project after adding the third layer.

There is major relation and impact based on accurate estimates of effort, cost, and schedule or timeline or delivery get failed, exceed budget and go overscheduled or bottleneck on work environment.

I had added the third Layer based on Three Layers Software Cost Estimation and the differences from actual cost and the derived cost from the Three Layers Based Software Cost Estimation meets the accuracy.

Software Effort and Cost estimation is the set of techniques and procedures that organize an estimate for proposal bidding, project planning and probability estimates.

Accurate Effort and Cost estimation means better planning and efficient use of project resources such as cost, duration and effort requirements for software projects.

Three Layers Based Software Cost Estimation methodology with an enhanced approach, focus on type of the domain of the Software Projects. The assessment of a Project based on Three Layers should be the first step for a Project manager before going to find the Cost or effort of the project.

Responsibility of the project manager is to have accurate estimates of effort, cost, and schedule involved in software development.

My approach meets the goal of any corporate Organization to achieve the best schedule and cost finding process for project manager, have accurate estimates of effort, cost, and schedule involved in software development.

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